

Stability constant of ternary complexes of copper(II) involving Schiff bases as primary ligands and amino acids as secondary ligands

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Abstract : The formation constant of mixed ligand complexes of copper(II) with Schiff bases 1-(2'-hydroxyl benzamido)-2-phenyl azomethine (L_1) and 1-(2'-hydroxyl benzamido)-2-(2-methyl phenyl) azomethine (L_2) as primary ligands and glycine (R_1), DL-valine (R_2) as secondary ligands have been determined potentiometrically in 40% (v/v) THF-water mixture at 30 °C and ionic strength of 0.1 M NaClO₄. The protonation constants of free ligands and stability constant for ternary systems involving Schiff bases and amino acids were also determined under identical conditions. The pH titration data were analysed using the computer SCOGS programme. The relative stability of ternary complexes as compared to that of corresponding binary complexes has been quantitatively explained in terms of $\Delta \log K$, K_R , K_L and K_T values.

Keywords : Schiff base, copper(II), amino acids, stability constant, ternary complex.

Introduction

In continuation of our earlier studies on binary and ternary complexes of Schiff bases¹, we have undertaken the study of complex equilibria of Cu^{II} complexes of some newly synthesized Schiff bases and also the ternary complexes of these Schiff bases as primary ligands and amino acids, glycine and DL-valine as secondary ligands.

Results and discussion

Binary complexes :

The protonation constants of primary ligands L_1 , L_2 and secondary ligands, glycine (R_1) and DL-valine (R_2) have been determined by Irving-Rossotti technique after appropriate pH corrections determined by using the method suggested by Van Uiter². Their stepwise metal-ligand formation constants (K_{ML}^H and K_{ML}^{ML}) were also determined for the comparison with those of the ternary systems under identical condition. The values are presented in Table 1. The primary as well as secondary ligands form both 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes with Cu^{II} ions. The complexing

tendency of Cu^{II} is found to be more with L_2 than L_1 .

Mixed ligand complexes :

The stability depends mainly on the ring size which affects the overall basicity of the secondary ligand. It can be inferred that the stability of complex depends more on the length and spatial configuration of chelate-ring than on the acidity of the complexing agent. At the pH of secondary ligand combination, the formation of mixed ligand can be represented by equilibria (1) and (2)

Only 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complexes have been used in this study to ensure the exclusive formation of the simplest ternary complex MLR. Considering the pK values of the ligands and hydrolytic constants of M^{2+} ions, the following species have been considered to exist in the complexation equilibria, M^{2+} , RH^2 , RH , R^{2-} , $M(OH)_2$, $MR(OH)$, MR , L^{2+} , $ML(OH)$, L^{2-} and $MRL(OH)$. The $\Delta \log K$, K_T , K_R and K_L parameters are generally used to indicate

Table 1. Protonation and metal-ligand stability constants in binary system

Ligand	K_1^H	K_2^H	$\log K_{ML}^M$	$\log K_{ML_2}^{ML}$
L_1 (C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂)	8.52	-	6.37	5.68
L_2 (C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂)	8.50	-	6.64	5.92
R_1	3.13	9.75	3.98	5.69
R_2	3.27	9.81	3.51	5.65

the relative stability of ternary complexes as compared to the binary complexes. These parameters are defined by the equations

$$\Delta \log K = \log \beta_{111} - \log K_{10} - \log K_{01} \quad (3)$$

$$K_r = \beta_{111}^2 / \beta_{20} \beta_{02} \quad (4)$$

$$K_R = \beta_{111} / \log K_{10} \quad (5)$$

$$K_L = \beta_{111} / \log K_{01} \quad (6)$$

The Schiff base L_1 and amino acid (glycine) R_1 both form 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes with Cu^{II} . The species distribution curves of CuL_1R_1 system indicates the formation of ternary complex. It can also be observed that the formation of L and HR represented by C_2 and C_3 shows continuous decrease with increasing pH and the concentration of these species is minimum at pH 4.5. The concentration of CuL is 14.27% at 3.5 pH and CuR is 17.57% at 3.5 pH which decrease with increasing pH value. The percentage concentration of CuR increase to 13.54% during this pH range. Concentration of CuL_2 remains negligible through out the pH range which confirms the formation of ternary complex by the reaction.

The comparison of β_{111} values with β_{20} of these systems reveals the preferential formation of ternary complexes over binary ones. The low values of K_R and K_L show more stability of ternary complexes with respect to binary complexes of primary and secondary ligands. The positive values of K_r also confirm the stability of mixed ligand complexes. The negative values of $\Delta \log K$ reveals that the stability of mixed ligands complex is comparable with 1 : 2 complex of binary species. The stability of 1 : 2 complex is less than the stability of 1 : 1 complex. Hence the stability of mixed ligand complex is less than the stability of 1 : 1 complex. In CuL_2R_1 system, the primary as well as secondary ligands individually form 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes with Cu^{II} . It has been observed from Table 2 that the stability of mixed ligand complexes of L_1 are found to be higher than that of the mixed ligand complexes of L_2 . The positive values of K_R , K_L and K_r show the stability of mixed ligand complexes but these

complexes are less stable than the 1 : 1 complexes of binary ones and hence we get negative values of $\Delta \log K$. The species distribution diagram of CuL_2R_1 system shows the similar trends as that of CuL_1R_1 system. Other systems, CuL_1R_2 and CuL_2R_2 also shows similar behavior.

The stability of binary species ML, MR and ternary species MLR complexes is in the expected order. The stability constant of ternary complexes were found to be greater in L_1 than in L_2 .

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade and all the solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water and standardized by usual procedure³. The Schiff bases 1-(2-hydroxyl benzamido)-2-phenyl azomethine (L_1) and 1-(2'-hydroxyl benzamido)-2-(2-methyl phenyl) azomethine (L_2) were synthesized by refluxing equimolar quantities of salicylhydrazine and respective aldehyde in ethanol for 6 h. The products obtained were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried over calcium chloride. The purity was tested by elemental analysis, melting point determination, TLC and IR spectra. The melting point of L_1 is 254 °C (Found : C, 69.74; H, 5.09; N, 11.83. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{12}O_2N_2$: C, 69.98; H, 5.03; N, 11.66%). The melting point of L_2 is 197 °C (Found : C, 70.21; H, 5.63; N, 11.21. Calcd. for $C_{15}H_{14}O_2N_2$: C, 70.84; H, 5.55; N, 11.02%). The two IR bands appearing at 1600–1630 cm^{-1} and 1190–1205 cm^{-1} were assigned to stretching vibration modes $\nu_{C=O}$, ν_{C-OH} deformation. The phenolic -OH stretching was found to be absent due to strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding with orthocarbonyl group. The observed lowering in normal carbonyl group frequency may be due to the effect of intramolecular hydrogen bonding.

The titrations were carried out using a digital pH meter (Elico model LI-120) in conjugation with combined electrode. All titrations were carried out at 30 ± 01 °C. For the determination of formation constants of ternary complexes, following solutions were prepared, 0.02 M perchloric acid, 0.01 M metal solutions at an ionic strength of 0.1 M sodium perchlorate. The titrations were plotted by using experimental data, which were utilized to ana-

Table 2. Stability constants of ternary complexes

L	R	β_{111}	β_{20}	β_{02}	K_R	K_L	K_r	$\Delta \log K$
L_1	Glycine	15.82	12.05	12.94	8.56	9.45	6.65	-2.19
L_1	DL-Valine	14.76	12.05	13.19	7.26	8.39	4.28	-0.89
L_2	Glycine	15.68	12.56	12.94	8.42	9.04	5.86	-1.78
L_2	DL-Valine	16.11	12.56	13.19	8.61	9.45	6.47	-1.95

Note

lyze the proton ligand formation constants of primary and secondary ligands and stability constants of their metal complexes. Concentration of total metal, total ligands, free metal, free ligand and various possible species that are formed during the complexation are calculated using SCOGS programme⁴. Complex formation equilibria were elucidated with the aid of species distribution curves obtained as computer output⁵.

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